

CDA NEWSLETTER

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BAYERO UNIVERSITY
KANO

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DRYLAND AGRICULTURE**
AN AFRICA CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

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- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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CDA CONDUCTS INTERNATIONAL TRAINING ON USE OF DSSAT MODEL

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano in collaboration with the West Africa Centre for Water, Irrigation and Sustainable Agriculture (WACWISA), University of Development Studies, Tamale, Ghana, has conducted an international training on the use of the DSSAT Model for the Assessment of Climate Risks and Environmental Sustainability in Smallholder Agricultural system.

The training was held at the WACWISA training hall from 31st October to 4th November 2022. All the 5 resource persons that anchored the training were from the CDA. The main objective of the training was to introduce participants to agricultural modeling in general with a focus on the DSSAT model.

The trainees were drawn from 13 different countries across disciplines, ranging from agricultural and irrigation engineers, crop breeders, soil scientists, agronomists, industry players and farm

managers. The moduled covered during the training include Modelling Agricultural Systems for Future Climate Scenarios over Africa, Simulating Water Limited Production, Simulating Nitrogen and Phosphorus Limited Production and Evaluating Climate Risks and Sustainability in Smallholder Agricultural Production Systems.

The training was done in a very interactive system usually starting with presentations supporting the theoretical bases of how DSSAT ran the various components, followed by a hands-on session, where participants were guided to model the various scenarios. The 5 day-training was quite impressive, as participants demonstrated very good understanding of the system at the end of the training.

A major take-away from the training was the evidence that many young, upcoming and even veteran scientists are still interested in learning and applying the DSSAT model in their various research areas and other applications. One of the participants said at the end of the training, "Thank you for demystifying the DSSAT model." It was a very satisfying moment for the trainers and the trainees. Overall, the whole exercise was a success.

Mid-Term Review: CDA Set to Get Additional World Bank Funds for Good Performance

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has achieved high scores in the mid-term assessment of the performances of the Africa Centres of Excellence for Development Impact (ACE Impact) project conducted by the World Bank. The information was conveyed on Monday, 7th November, 2022 by Mr Harry Gerard Crimi, Jnr in his presentation during the Nigeria country roundtable between the World Bank, the French Development Agency (AFD), and the 17 Nigerian ACEs. With this development, CDA will receive additional funds from the World Bank.

Also to receive additional funding is BUK's Africa Centre of Excellence in Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP).

The ACE Impact project is a higher education initiative funded by the World Bank and AFD, which formally took-off in 2019 in eleven countries of West and Central Africa. The aim of the project is to establish strong specialized regional centres that focus on thematic areas and provide world-class training, research and outreach focused on addressing the development challenges of Africa. The Centres were competitively selected, and BUK emerged as one of the few Universities with more than one ACE. The initial grant to CDA was five million US dollars and that of ACEPHAP six million.

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Director, CDA Prof. Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin at the World Bank headquarters

In the implementation of the ACE Impact project, the World Bank employs a “results-based” funding approach in which funds are released to the Centres based on performance and achievement of key milestones. After taking stock of the performances of all the Centres during the mid-term review of the project, the high-performing centres will be given additional funds while poorly performing centres will have their initial allocation reduced.

It could be recalled that in the first phase of the ACE project (2014-2019), CDA got an initial grant of about seven million US Dollars and an additional amount of one million US dollars following its excellent performance at mid-term.

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, has congratulated the two Centres for their excellent performance and for positively projecting the image of BUK globally.

It could be recalled that in the first phase of the ACE project (2014-2019), CDA got an initial grant of about seven million US Dollars and an additional amount of one million US dollars following its excellent performance at mid-term

Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (middle) explaining a point to the World Bank President, Mr David Malpass (left), while CDA regional PhD student from Tanzania, Rehema looks on in smile

CDA Participates at ACE Impact Project Meeting in Gambia

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture was applauded for attaining 59% rating at mid-term of the ACE-Impact project having achieved 100% in research publications, programme accreditation, external revenue generation and 87% in internships.

The commendation and applause took place at the 8th Regional Workshop of the Africa Centres of Excellence (ACE) Impact Project held from 14th - 18th November, 2022 in Banjul Gambia. The Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, led the CDA team.

The workshop with the theme **'Innovation and Entrepreneurship,'** took place at the Sir Dawda Kairaba Jawara International Conference Centre. Plenary and Discussions and breakout sessions largely centered on *'Innovations in Higher Education in Africa: A post-covid era perspective.'*

Strategies and pathways for establishing world-class universities while identifying multiple challenges, costs and risks associated with these approaches in the post-covid era were discussed. Alternative perspectives on how African countries can innovate to develop effective and relevant tertiary education systems to meet their specific needs looking at leveraging digital technologies for teaching and strengthening innovations in research were also identified.

The creation of synergies and partnerships across countries and sectors towards building a stronger higher education sector that addresses the contradiction of unemployed graduates, the lack of skilled workforce and low research output in the African continent were the main thrust of the 4-day workshop.

The workshop discussed strengthening the economy of African countries by improving knowledge transfer between universities and companies, while promoting innovation

The Vice Chancellor in a group photograph with the CDA-ACE Team shortly after the workshop was declared open. Left – right: Usman G. Ohikere (Finance Officer), Dr Bashir Musa (Environmental Safeguards Officer), Dr Yusuf Garba (Project Manager), Prof. Sanusi G. Mohammed (Deputy Centre Leader), Prof. Sagir A. Abbas (Vice Chancellor), Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin (Centre Leader), Prof. Amina Mustapha (Monitoring and Evaluation Officer) and Rabiu H. Sagagi (Procurement Officer)

through research and entrepreneurship.

Prominent in the disbursement linked indicators (DLIs) featured centered on: programme accreditation, institutional accreditation, institutional Impact, entrepreneurship and innovation and research publications.

Like every workshop, the key takeaways at the end of the workshop were:

- Creating policies and opportunities for all
- Strengthening university management involvement in the project
- Unblocking procurement prioritize bottlenecks

- Greater attention to innovation and entrepreneurship (DLI 5.3)
- Pending ESMPs to be completed.

Earlier, during the welcome address, the Secretary-General of the AAU stated that an important milestone in the lifeline of the ACE-Impact project was that *'the project is at the threshold of mid-term review.'*

With this assertion and impressive performance of the CDA at mid-term review, there is no gain-saying that the theme "Innovation and Entrepreneurship" underscores the need to maximize the potential of human capital in the African continent'.

Cross section of CDA and ACEPHAP teams, as well as the participants during one of the plenary sessions

CDA and ACEPHAP Set Over N1 Billion to Support BUK's Digital Education, Landscape

Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) and Director ACEPHAP, Prof. Hadiza Galadanci at World Bank headquarters

The Africa Centre of Excellence for Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP) and Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) have set aside 10% of their combined grants from the Africa Centres of Excellence for Development Impact totaling over 1 billion Naira to support Bayero University's digital landscape as part of the initiative to make significant impact in the community.

Professor Jibrin added that World Bank and French Development Agency wanted the Africa centres to make institutional impact as contained in DLI 7, saying that the idea was to support the landscape of BUK. He said the two centres were working to improve the

internet connectivity of the university and impact positively on many other areas.

The areas to be supported include teaching, research, internet connectivity, digital education, etc.

This was contained in a speech delivered by the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, at the opening session of a 5-day training on Innovation and Intellectual Property organized by the ACEPHAP and BUK

He said the centres had been impacting positively to the university's teaching, research and community services and based on their advice, the University Management would review the alumni system.

According to him, the two centres had put a proposal to the World Bank to make BUK a centre of competence in digital education. He happily told the participants there were 53 of those centres in Africa and BUK was competitively chosen as one of only 6 institutions in this regard.

He added that the World Bank had also approved the purchase of modern studio equipment to boost digital education in BUK. In this regard, he said there were some trainings for 30 BUK staff, who would later train others.

Speaking earlier, the Director ACEPHAP, Professor Hadiza Galadanci, said the objective of the training was to change the narratives of conducting research on publishing papers only to a one that at the end of the day would either change policy or patent it to have economic growth that made a significant impact on the lives of the people.

She said BUK was lucky to have two Africa centres of excellence for development impact and that the World Bank wanted the centres in a few years to come to have patents developed by researchers and improve the income generation of the university, centres and individual researchers.

Papers were presented by Professor I.A. Rufai, the Director of DRIP on Innovation and Entrepreneurship Ecosystem in BUK; Concept and Significance of Applied Research in Innovation by Professor Yakasai Ibrahim Adamu, Deputy Director, Research, Innovation and Partnership, DRIP; Dr Jaamil Ismail, Problems of Healthcare in Nigeria; Agricultural Innovation: Past, Present and the Future by Deputy Director Outreach and Publications, CDA.

Director ACEPHAP, Professor Hadiza Galadanci addressing the participants

BUK was lucky to have two Africa centres of excellence for development impact. The World Bank wants the centres to have patents developed by researchers and improve the income generation of the university, centres and individual researchers

CDA Deputy Director, Outreach and Publications, Prof Amina Mustapha addressing the participants

CDA Trains Women, Farmers on Groundnut Seeds Production

Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has trained farmers from 22 adopted communities neighboring Bayero University, Kano on the new improved methods of groundnut seeds production under the AVISA Project.

The Deputy Director CDA, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, said training was organized to educate farmers on the new methods of groundnut production. He said the 22 communities were those neighbouring the university and those to first benefit with the training.

He said it was quite imperative to bring experts and technocrats who specialized in improved groundnut production to the training with the hope that people would learn and adopt it. He said the importance of this was that people had encountered myriad challenges on groundnut farming, but it was good to channel the new technology to the farmers, especially those communities neighboring Bayero University.

According to him, the training was centred around selection of seeds, sowing, harvesting and storage. "We are aware that farmers encounter challenges of pests and other diseases. This training would bring to fore how to overcome those challenges," he added.

Deputy Director, Training of CDA, Prof. Sanusi Gaya Mohammed

Prof Gaya noted that it was the responsibility of the researchers to inform the farmers the outcome of their researches, so that farmers would use them to improve their productivity, hoping that they would also train other farmers, who were not present.

Presenting a paper on Groundnut Seed Production, Dr. Abdulwahab Saliu Shaibu said Seed was the vital input and driver in crop production, as seed quality determined the return on investment made on other inputs like fertilizer, irrigation, pesticide, labour etc, and that a poor seed quality would result in poor return

despite best investment on other farm inputs.

Explaining the nutritive value of groundnut, Dr. Shaibu said it was considered as low sodium food and free from cholesterol and contained less than 20% saturated fatty acid hence heart friendly.

According to him, groundnut seed contains 44-55% oil and 22-30% protein on a dry seed and was a rich source of mineral (phosphorus, calcium, magnesium and potassium) and vitamins E, K and the B group.

In terms of field requirement, Dr Abdulwahab said farmers should avoid areas prone to excess rains and high humidity. Such

A female farmer making her contribution

weather conditions, he said, may cause disease proliferation, delayed maturity and pre-harvest germination of seed in many cases.

On the issue of site selection, he told the farmers to avoid soil that was hard and resistant to peg penetration, field previously cultivated with groundnut and clay soils.

In terms of seed treatment, the presenter called them to treat the seed with dressing chemical such as Apron plus, Thiram, Mancozeb @ 3g per kg seed before sowing. This is because they would help to prevent diseases, insect/rodents' attack, reduce seed-borne infection and vigorous stand.

In his paper on Weed Management in Groundnut Production, Dr A. Lado said weeds had economic importance as they increase pest and disease incidence and their severity; increased the cost of production; reduce the economic values of lands, e.g. Alectra; they caused health hazard for man and other animals; limited the choice of land e.g. parasitic weeds, and interfered with water management under irrigated conditions.

He said there are preventive measures in controlling weeds, such as fallowing, preventing weed from setting seeds, the use of clean crop seeds for planting and the use of clean machinery. Others, he said, were controlled movement of livestock and quarantine measures.

Dr Haruna Salisu Gombe, who presented a paper titled: PREHARVEST AND POST HARVEST MANAGEMENT OF AFLATOXINS CONTAMINATION IN GROUNDNUT VALUE CHAIN, said research had shown that 25% of world food crops, including groundnut were contaminated with aflatoxins.

He stated that Aflatoxins were produced before, during and after harvesting, which affected crop quality and safety for human consumption, noting that groundnut was one of the main sources of human exposure to aflatoxins.

According to him Aflatoxin contamination could lead to chronic and acute toxicity, and

cause death in mammals, birds and fish, as well as in humans.

He said farmers had minimal control on environmental factors; however, they could improve agricultural practices used in crop production to reduce fungal infection, growth and aflatoxin production

The trainees expressed appreciation to the CDA for impacting positively on their lives by equipping them with the right training and skills for improved agricultural production. They admitted that through such trainings, farming had been boosted and communities recorded high yields.

Seed is the vital input and driver in crop production, as seed quality determines the return on investment made on other inputs like fertilizer, irrigation, pesticide, labour etc, and that a poor seed quality will result in poor return despite best investment on other farm inputs

CDA Conducts Farmers' Field Day on Early Generation Seed Production

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) has conducted a farmers' field day on early generation seed production under the AVISA Project of the centre held at Doka for 22 adopted communities in 5 local governments of Kano State.

The CDA's Deputy Director of Training, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed, who is a groundnut seed breeder, said the CDA grows foundation seeds of groundnut and extended them to farmers to grow certified seeds, noting that the centre trained farmers on improved seed production practices.

He said through the centre's intervention, many farmers had now become seed producers, citing some farmers whose livelihood had greatly improved and employed the services of labour.

Abubakar M. Inuwa, the Extension Agent of the area, said farmers in those communities had adopted the new improved varieties provided by the CDA, noting that economic opportunities had improved as farmers recorded high yields.

Many farmers interviewed testified that the improved groundnuts are differed especially Samnut 24, which is early maturing, compared to the local types.

Similarly, Women Farmer Groups at the Yakasai Community of Bichi Local Government said the CDA intervention had boosted their production and encouraged many others to venture into farming as a source of their livelihood.

The leader of Yakasai Alheri Women Farmers Association, Rabi Samaila, said CDA gave them early maturing seeds in which 30 women benefitted. She said the association had over 100 women, who benefitted from the CDA support.

A scene of farmers' field day organised by CDA under AVISA Project

Deputy Director, Training of CDA, Prof. Sanusi Gaya Mohammed addressing the farmers

A cross section of participants during the occasion

Kubura Ibrahim Yakasai and Binta Mamuda said they have employed many women farmers in their farms courtesy of the CDA intervention. They said the improved varieties have completely changed their status as their income has greatly improved.

CDA Inaugurates Four Thematic Research Groups, Budgets \$120,000

Director CDA addressing team leaders of CDA thematic research groups

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture on Thursday, 22nd December, 2022 inaugurated four thematic research groups with the aim of having focused and impactful research that will provide solutions to development challenges in African drylands.

The Director of CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, who led the inauguration, said the idea was to make an impact through research activities, noting that "If we allow everybody to do whatever kind of research he wants then we are not going to make any serious impact. So, that's the idea of setting up thematic areas in which we will provide support for research groups to form along those areas and I think it's going to be a very good thing not only for CDA but also for members of the group," he said.

According to him, CDA had set up four research groups about two years ago, "but unfortunately at that time we didn't have resources to support the groups' take off. We started getting funds from the project just towards the end of last year and immediately after that, we went into a very long strike so it was not possible for those groups to do much. So, we sat down and discussed, and agreed to set up thematic areas rather than research groups," he said.

The Director pointed out that within each thematic area, several groups were expected to be formed. The idea was to encourage multi-disciplinary and inter-disciplinary research within the themes.

According to him, the Centre had budgeted \$120,000 for the take-off activities of the thematic research groups, with each group taking \$30,000. He said CDA students would be fully involved in the thematic research.

Speaking on behalf of the research groups, Professor Aliyu Barau thanked the CDA for selecting them to lead the thematic research groups and expressed confidence that a positive outcome would come out from the activities of the thematic groups.

The four thematic research areas with their leaders are:

- i. Crop Improvement and Management, to be led by Prof. M.A. Hussaini
- ii. Livestock Improvement and Management, to be led by Prof. A.M. Abdussamad
- iii. Livelihood and Environment, to be led by Prof. A.S. Barau
- iv. Bioresources, to be led by Prof. M. Abdulazeez

CDA Inaugurates Four Thematic Research Groups, Budgets \$120,000

PHOTO NEWS

Team lead of Crop Improvement and Management, Prof. M.A. Hussaini (right) receiving his letter of appointment from CDA Director

Team lead of Livelihood and Environment, Prof. A.S. Barau (right) receiving his letter of appointment from Director CDA, Prof. J.M. Jibrin

Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) presenting a letter of appointment to Team lead of Bioresources, Prof. M. Abdulazeez

Team lead of Livestock Improvement and Management, Prof. A.M. Abdussamad (right) receiving his letter of appointment

A group photograph of CDA Team and leaders of four Thematic Research groups

Prof Jibrin Takes over from Prof Tona as President of Food for West Africa

The Director Center of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, has taken over as the new President of Food for West Africa. He has succeeded Professor Kokou Tona, the Director of Center of Excellence for Poultry Science (CERSA) of Togo.

The election took place at the end of the second general assembly of the network, which was held in mixed mode (physical and virtual meeting) on December 1, 2022, at Abuja, Nigeria.

In his speech, the new President said he would do his utmost to accelerate the activities of the network in order to achieve its objectives. 'I know that there are many challenges ahead of us, but with everyone's commitment, we will overcome them,' said the network's newly elected president, Professor Jibrin.

The general assembly through the administrative secretary of the network, Prof. Kossi Métoogo, presented the activities and the financial reports and the election of the new president of the network. During a round table discussion, the participants present at the assembly insisted on the ways and means to be adopted to accelerate the execution of the various activities assigned to the centers.

The assembly of agriculture based Africa Centre's of Excellence was organized on the sidelines of the second edition of the conference for the promotion of local African products and the mitigation of problems related to post-harvest losses organized by the Center of Excellence for Food Technology and Research (CEFTER) of the Benue State University, Makurdi, Nigeria.

"This edition of the conference was dedicated to local African foods most of which are neglected, poorly preserved and vastly underutilized, despite their crucial role in food

Prof. Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin (right) takes over as the new President of Food for West Africa, Professor Kokou Tona (left), the Director of Center of Excellence for Poultry Science (CERSA), Togo

security, nutrition, medicinal values and income generation for humanity," stated the organizers. According to them, "The promotion of these local foods, especially amongst the rural dwellers, will not only help to sustainably fight against hunger in Africa but also to gain inclusion in the global food system".

A special panel was devoted to the Food for West Africa network. It was a great opportunity for its leaders to present the objectives, missions and actions of the network in favor of food security in Africa.

Food for West Africa is a group of seven Africa centers of excellence dedicated to the agricultural sector.

The seven centers that make up the network are:

- Regional Center of Excellence for Poultry Science (CERSA) of Togo;
- Regional Center of Excellence on Pastoral Production (CERPP) in Niger;
- Centre For Food Technology and Research (CEFTER) of Nigeria;
- Climate Change, Biodiversity and Sustainable Agriculture (CCBAD) of Côte d'Ivoire;
- African Center of Excellence in Dryland Agriculture (CDA) of Nigeria;
- African Center of Excellence in Agriculture for Food and Nutritional Security (AGRISAN) of Senegal;
- West Africa Center for Crop Improvement (WACCI) of Ghana.

A group photograph of some of the participants

PHOTO GALLERY OF A 5-DAY TRAINING ON INNOVATION AND INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY ORGANIZED BY CDA AND ACEPHAP IN OCTOBER 2022

Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin addressing the participants

The Director ACEPHAP, Prof Hadiza Galadanci commenting on the workshop

Deputy Director Outreach and Publications of CDA, Prof Amina Mustapha (left) explaining a point to the Director CDA, Prof Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin

Dr Murtala M. Badamasi speaking at the workshop

Dr Kabir Mustapha Umar, Deputy Director Training of CDA (right) presenting a certificate to one of the participants

ACEPHAP's M&E Officer, Dr. Baba Maiyaki presenting certificate to Dr Murtala Uba of Geography Department

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